

MATERIAL SELECTION FOR FUNCTIONALIZED FIBER-REINFORCED COMPOSITE STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

- The paper investigates **material selection** for functionalized structures and active materials, particularly piezoelectric materials, for integration in design and manufacturing phases.
- Study proposes **PVDF (Polyvinylidene fluoride)** as the active element and **pre-impregnated unidirectional flax fiber** as the base material for creating **smart composite structures** capable of fracture detection and monitoring.
- Selection process considers **insulation capacity, curing temperature, and production process** of the smart composite in choosing the host fiber-reinforced composite material.
- Testing includes creating symmetrical laminated composites and conducting vibration tests with magnetic manipulation on the smart materials.
- Future work suggestions: exploring diverse **fabrication methodologies**, investigating piezoelectric sensor **placement configurations'** signal response, and utilizing advanced **finite element analysis** to validate interlaminar stress impact.

OBJECTIVES

- To select appropriate materials for functionalized structures, particularly piezoelectric materials, for potential integration during the design and manufacturing phases.
- To embed piezo-based sensors into a composite material structure during fabrication instead of attaching external sensors.

- To create new aeronautical structures capable of detecting and monitoring fractures.
- To investigate the functional properties of the resulting smart materials through vibration tests with magnetic manipulation.

METHODS

Sample Fabrication Process:

Sample's lamination scheme.

Consolidation molding process.

Smart composite structure

Sample's impedance/conductivity test.

Composite's Fiber Type	Electrical Continuity	Resistance
Carbon	Yes	0 Ω
Flax	No	830.7 MΩ

Electrical conductivity test results

Sample Experimental Tests :

Test for structural integrity

To assess the impact of the embedded PVDF in the structure and the wire adhesion status, a 5mm by 50mm pieces were subjected to micro computed tomography.

X-ray micro computed tomography

Sensitivity tests and electromechanical characterization

Vibration tests setup

RESULTS

Integration's Impact on the Structural Integrity

- UD - FlaxPreg – with variational density of fibers
- Defects sustained from the raw material
- Defects due to embedding
- Resin pocket

Sensitivity Analysis

Composite Number	Number of Layers Stacking sequence [0°/90°/0°] _s	Position of Piezo Layer	Pk-Pk Voltage (mV)	RMS Voltage (mV)	Resonance Frequency (Hz)
Sample 1	6	Layers 3-4	108.93	34.67	41.21
Sample 2	6	Layers 4-5	770.30	261.6	42.15
Sample 3	6	Layers 5-6	3017.60	1048	40.60

- The sensitivity test results from dynamic loading of the smart composite laminates. The peak to peak and the true RMS voltages were measured at resonance

CONCLUSIONS

- The selection of appropriate constituent materials plays a critical role in the context of smart composite structures.
- PVDF has proven to be highly beneficial in reducing thickness variation and preventing fiber cutting, making it a suitable material for embedded sensors.
- Dynamic vibration tests have confirmed the feasibility of implementing PVDF in aeronautical structures, establishing its reliability for applications requiring embedded sensors.
- The study's results demonstrate the potential of using pre-impregnated unidirectional flax fiber as the base material for creating new aeronautical structures capable of detecting and monitoring fractures.
- The study's findings provide a foundation for future research on the development of smart composite materials with enhanced performance and reliability.

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